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NUMERICAL ASSESSMENT OF AN OPEN ROTOR 1P LOADS AT TAKE-OFF AND CRUISE

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ABSTRACT

Unsteady in-plane forces, also referred to as 1P loads, are a critical aspect in open rotor propulsion systems due to their influence on vibration, aeroelastic stability, and structural fatigue. Their accurate quantification is therefore fundamental for both aerodynamic performance evaluation and structural design. This study presents a methodology for assessing 1P loads and their structural implications using an open-rotor geometry representative of modern open-fan concepts. High-fidelity full-annulus CFD simulations were performed for take-off and cruise conditions, using dedicated meshing strategies to resolve unsteady flow features at angles of attack of up to 30° and 6°, respectively. The global loads are decomposed into thrust and in-plane components, with a focus on the 1P harmonic. Unsteady pressures are then projected onto the first bending mode of the blade to obtain modal forces, which are coupled with a single-degree-of-freedom oscillator to predict vibration amplitudes and alternating stresses. Results show that the projection step is critical, as global force harmonics alone fail to estimate the effective dynamic excitation. The approach enables a direct evaluation of vibration amplitudes, indicating that oscillation amplitudes remain below 1% of the blade span. This approach provides a reliable method for the detailed design and fatigue assessment of open-fan blades.

NOMENCLATURE

CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
FEM	Finite Element Model
USF	Unducted Single Fan
ORAS	Open Rotor And Stator
CROR	Counter-Rotating Open Rotor
RANS	Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes equations
OGV	Outlet Guide Vane
SDOF	Single degree of freedom
FSI	Fluid Structure Interaction
OP	Operating Point
EO	Engine order
AoA	Angle of Attack
f	Blade natural frequency [Hz]
A_f	Amplification factor
C_T	$= F_x / \rho n^2 D^4$. Thrust coefficient
C_{1P}	$= F_{1P} / \rho n^2 D^4$. In-plane force coefficient
p_s	Static pressure
T_s	Static temperature
H	Rotor blade span
D	Rotor Diameter
J	Advance ratio
F	Blade Force
F_{mod}	Modal force
c	Axial chord
V_0	Free stream speed
P_0	Dynamic pressure
Ma	$= V_0 / \sqrt{(\gamma R_{air} T)}$. Mach number

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n	Rotor Rotational Speed
k	Normalized harmonic amplitude
$\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})$	Blade surface element normal vector
B.C.s	Boundary Conditions

Greek symbols

ρ	Density
Ω	Shaft Speed [rad/s]
ω_n	Natural frequency
β	Blade pitch angle
α	Inflow angle
Ψ	In-plane force phase angle
$\phi(\mathbf{x})$	Mode-shape eigenvector
θ	Azimuthal angle

Sub-scripts

ax	Axial direction
0	Free stream
1P	In-plane component
s	Static
cr	Cruise
TO	Take-off

Super-scripts

/	First harmonic
$\hat{}$	Frequency domain
\sim	Normalized value

INTRODUCTION

The aviation sector is subject to increasing constraints on fuel efficiency and environmental performance. Current research, therefore, addresses not only the refinement of turbofan engines but also the development of alternative propulsion architectures capable of delivering substantial improvements in efficiency and emissions reduction. Open rotor configurations have re-emerged as promising propulsion systems for the next generation of short and medium-range aircrafts, especially within the single-aisle segment. Their open architecture offers the potential for significant gains in propulsive efficiency, but also introduces complex aerodynamic and structural challenges.

One of the most critical issues concerns the aerodynamic forces acting transverse to the axis of rotation of the propellers, generally referred to as in-plane forces or 1P loads. These forces originate from non-uniformities in the incoming flow field, which may arise from inflow distortion, installation effects, or operation at a nonzero angle of attack. Under these conditions, each rotor blade experiences variations in relative velocity and incidence throughout the revolution, resulting in unsteady aerodynamic loading.

The accurate prediction of 1P loads is of paramount importance, as these unsteady forces directly affect propeller and engine structural design. They contribute to vibration transmission, can initiate aeroelastic instabilities such as flutter,

and are of primary importance in fatigue analysis by driving alternating stresses on the blades and associated structures[1]. Although a range of computational tools has been employed for propeller analysis, from simplified lifting-line approaches to high-fidelity three-dimensional CFD, the reliable estimation of 1P loads remains challenging due to the inherently unsteady and three-dimensional nature of the problem.

The study of aerodynamic forces acting on propellers at a nonzero angle of attack has a long history, motivated by the need to understand and predict the origin of in-plane loads. Harris and Glauert [2, 3] developed the earliest theoretical models, establishing an analogy between an inclined propeller and a lifting fin. Their formulations expressed the additional normal force and moment components in terms of the thrust and torque of an axisymmetric propeller. The analytical modelling was later extended by Ribner [4, 5], who developed a more comprehensive model that incorporated the blade planform geometry. Ribner derived closed-form expressions for the side force and yawing moment, achieving good agreement with measurements up to approximately 20° incidence. De Young [6] subsequently refined Ribner’s approach, applying simplifications to the integrations and introducing corrections for higher incidence angles. These extensions improved applicability but still exhibited divergence near edgewise flow, where the underlying assumptions break down. Crigler [7] developed a model based on blade element momentum theory (BEMT) for a propeller operating in non-axial flight conditions, assuming locally uniform inflow conditions for each annular blade section. This approach reproduced radial variations in blade loading. Despite these advancements, analytical and semi-empirical methods remain constrained in their applicability. Widely used expressions, such as those of de Young [6], have proven effective for isolated propellers at incidence and have been adapted to include the influence of fuselage and wing-induced inflows in tractor configurations [8].

Analytical formulations provided rapid estimates of propeller aerodynamics but were restricted to incompressible, low-speed conditions. The development of CFD approaches was driven by the need to capture transonic effects and to model the aerodynamic behaviour of realistic 3D blade geometries.

Euler and Navier–Stokes solvers have since been applied to propellers and open rotors at incidence. Brandvik et al. [9, 10] investigated the interaction between the front rotor wake, tip vortices, and the rear rotor, primarily for aeroacoustic applications. However, numerical predictions of in-plane forces on open rotors remain unvalidated. Ortun et al. [11] performed a comparison with experimental data for an isolated single propeller, obtaining good agreement at low Mach numbers but increasing deviations at higher speeds.

Calavera et al. [12] proposes a work addressing 1P loads in the context of fatigue, focused on the application of CFD and FEM coupling to installed propellers. This approach enabled the prediction of static loads and vibration environments, including

FIGURE 1. SKETCH OF THE OPEN VIRTUAL TEST CASE.

OPERATING POINTS	CRUISE	TAKE-OFF
ALTITUDE [m]	10,668	0
FLIGHT MACH	0.78	0.25
ROTOR SPEED [RPM]	983	1228
V_0 [m/s]	231.2	87.27
p_s [Pa]	23,842	101,325
T_s [K]	218.8	303.1
ρ [kg/m^3]	0.38	1.16
PITCH SETTING		
ROTOR	0°	+19.7°
STATOR (OGV)	0°	-10.2°

TABLE 1. OPERATING POINTS AND PITCH SETTINGS.

aeroelastic effects. Billmann et al. [13, 14] reported on open-fan dynamic loads within NASA’s ATP program. Their analysis of harmonic 1P loads was limited to aerodynamic simulations which were coupled solely with torsional deformation. To date, this type of analysis has not been extended to a modern Open Fan geometry with swirl recovery.

In this work, a modern open rotor geometry with swirl recovery designed by the PANDORA consortium[15], and introduced in [16], is used to numerically investigate the impact of 1P loads on blade elastic deformations. The first part of the paper outlines the computational setup and mesh characteristics, followed by an evaluation of in-plane forces for take-off and cruise conditions at nonzero angle of attack. This constitutes an initial step toward verifying the prediction of in-plane loads and assessing the consistency of the CFD results. The second part of the paper introduces a methodology for estimating the maximum blade deflection under 1P loading and identifying the most critical operating configurations.

OPEN VIRTUAL TEST CASE

The geometry used in this work corresponds to the open-fan configuration released within the PANDORA project (www.pandora-project.com), also referred to as an Unducted Single Fan (USF) or Open Rotor and Stator (ORAS). This configuration is the result of an industrially driven design process [15], which ensures realistic aerodynamic and structural characteristics. The virtual test case consists of a single rotor with 12 blades and a stator with 8 vanes, forming an open-fan system with a diameter of $D = 3.96$ m (13 ft) (Fig. 1). The design target of the model corresponds to a thrust level of roughly 90 kN during take-off and 17 kN during cruise. Details of the blade and hubline geometry are documented in [15]. Both rotors and stators are designed with variable pitch, allowing pitch settings

to be adapted for different operating conditions, as summarized in Table 1. The aerodynamic characteristics of the steady flow at cruise and take-off have been reported in [16].

Structural model

To assess the structural response of the open-rotor configuration under 1P aerodynamic loading, a finite element model (FEM) of the rotor blade was developed. The stator vanes were not included in this analysis, since they are not directly subjected to oscillatory 1P excitations; the inflow angle primarily modifies their mean loading rather than inducing cyclic variations. Consequently, only the rotor blade was structurally modeled.

The rotor blade was represented as a solid component with homogeneous material properties of approximately 230,000 tetrahedral elements (Fig. 2 a), adopting titanium as the reference alloy due to its widespread use in rig testing even though it is generally admitted that the open rotor actual design will feature a composite blade. The material properties used in the model were: Young’s modulus $E = 116$ GPa, Poisson’s ratio $\nu = 0.34$, and density $\rho = 4500$ kg/m^3 . The root section of the blade was clamped to represent the rigid connection with the hub, and the centrifugal stiffening effects were included as shown in Figure 2.a. Modal analysis was subsequently performed using the open-source solver CalculiX v2.20, from which the blade-alone first bending mode was extracted (Fig. 2 b). The associated natural frequency was found to be $f_{cr} = 28.6$ Hz at cruise and $f_{TO} = 31.8$ Hz at take-off. The Campbell diagram presented in Fig. 3 confirms that, within the investigated operating range, no critical crossings occur between the blade natural frequencies and the engine excitation orders.

FIGURE 2. FEM DISCRETIZATION OF THE ROTOR BLADE (A). VELOCITY MAGNITUDE OF THE FIRST MODE-SHAPE (B).

FIGURE 3. CAMPBELL DIAGRAM; THE FREQUENCIES OF FOUR MODE-SHAPE ARE IDENTIFIED WITH COLORED SOLID LINES. THE ENGINE ORDERS ARE HIGHLIGHTED WITH BLACK SOLID LINES.

Aeroelastic model

Unsteady simulations of open-rotor configurations at nonzero angles of attack require the use of a full-annulus computational domain, since the inflow conditions differ for each blade depending on its azimuthal position. The computational setup adopts a multi-block structured topology, bounded by a cylindrical outer domain (Fig. 4). Two sliding-plane interfaces are used to couple the rotating and stationary blocks. The rotor

FIGURE 4. SKETCH OF THE AEROELASTIC DOMAIN. DETAIL OF THE MESH CHARACTERISTICS OF THE SLIDING PLANE AND OF THE BLADES.

and spinner domains rotate at the prescribed speed, whereas the stator (OGV) remains stationary. The mesh was generated in two stages: first, detailed meshing of rotor and stator was performed; subsequently, the domain was radially extended to reach the far-field boundary (Fig. 4). The spinner block was constructed by azimuthal extrusion of a two-dimensional mesh. The near-blade resolution matches that employed in [16], where the same configuration was validated against steady-flow results from independent solvers. Specifically, the rotor discretization consists of 75 radial layers and 200 circumferential points per layer, resulting in a global mesh size of approximately 39 million nodes. The rotor blades and hub were modeled as no-slip walls, while uniform conditions were prescribed at the far-field boundary.

The flow solver employed is HADES, an in-house code developed specifically for aerospace propulsion applications. Its verification and validation against a broad set of compressor flows are reported in He et al. [17, 18]. The solver is second-order accurate in space and time, based on a finite-volume, node-centered formulation with edge-based fluxes. Convective fluxes are computed using the Jameson–Schmidt–Turkel (JST) scheme, and turbulence closure is provided by the Spalart–Allmaras model with wall-function treatment. For the aeroelastic coupling, the blade mode shape is interpolated onto the fluid mesh. A fluid–structure interaction (FSI) module without mesh motion is employed within the

OP	Ma	J	β [deg]	α [deg]
Take-off	0.25	1.07	19.7	0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30
Cruise	0.78	3.56	0	0, 2, 4, 6

TABLE 2. TEST MATRIX.

URANS framework to evaluate modal forces. Each unsteady computation is advanced in a time-accurate manner for at least four rotor revolutions to ensure convergence of the unsteady loads. The computational cost of each unsteady simulation amounts to approximately 72 hours when run on an AMD EPYC 7713 128-core CPU, with a temporal resolution of 0.5° rotor rotation per time step.

METHODOLOGY

A series of unsteady full-annulus CFD simulations with rigid blades were performed at inflow angles up to $\alpha = 30^\circ$ for take-off and $\alpha = 6^\circ$ for cruise. The corresponding operating conditions are summarized in Table 2.

The analysis begins with the evaluation of the global aerodynamic forces acting on the rotor stage. These forces are obtained by summing the contributions of all blades in the rotor. The total load is then decomposed into two components: the axial force or thrust, F_x , along the rotation axis and the in-plane force within the propeller plane (YZ-plane). For convenience, the in-plane load is further expressed in terms of its modulus, F_{1P} and phase angle, Ψ , a decomposition commonly adopted in the literature [19, 20] and described in Fig. 1 as

$$F_{1P} = \sqrt{F_y^2 + F_z^2} \quad \Psi = \arctan(F_z/F_y) \cdot 180/\pi \quad (1)$$

The global aerodynamic forces acting on the rotor are presented in nondimensional form by using the main metrics that drive the design of Open Fans, which has been also used to define the performance of the virtual test case in [16]. The advance ratio, J , is defined as:

$$J = \frac{V_0}{nD} \quad (2)$$

where n is the rotational speed in Hz, V_0 the free stream velocity modulus, and D the rotor blade tip diameter. The thrust, F_x , and the in-plane force, F_{1P} , are similarly nondimensionalized as:

$$C_T = \frac{F_x}{\rho n^2 D^4} \quad C_{1P} = \frac{F_{1P}}{\rho n^2 D^4} \quad (3)$$

Subsequently, the unsteady blade loads are examined. At this level, the pressure and force distributions are expressed in their Cartesian components, which allows direct projection onto the aircraft reference system, following the same approach as in [11]. To characterise their spectral content, a fast Fourier transform (FFT) is applied to the blade force signals over one complete rotor revolution in the blade relative frame. The chosen

FIGURE 5. SKETCH OF THE YZ-PLANE. DETAIL OF THE IN-PLANE FORCE, F_{1P} AND THE IN-PLANE PHASE ANGLE, Ψ .

time step ensures accurate resolution of all frequencies up to the third harmonic of the blade passing frequency.

After extracting the 1P harmonic loads for both take-off and cruise conditions, the aerodynamic forcing is projected onto the first bending mode of the blade to obtain the modal force. The instantaneous modal force is given by:

$$F_{mod}(t) = \int_{\Sigma} p(\mathbf{x}, t) (\phi(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})) dS \quad (4)$$

where $p(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the unsteady pressure, $\mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})$ the outward normal vector and $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ the normalized structural mode shape. To isolate the harmonic content of the excitation, the pressure is transformed into the frequency domain via a Fourier transform:

$$\hat{p}(\mathbf{x}, \omega) = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T p(\mathbf{x}, t) e^{-i\omega t} dt \quad (5)$$

where ω is the vibration angular frequency related to the 1P excitation and T is the vibration period. Consequently, the modal force at 1P frequency, ω , is:

$$\hat{F}_{mod}(\omega) = \int_{\Sigma} \hat{p}(\mathbf{x}, \omega) (\phi(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})) dS. \quad (6)$$

The structural response is modeled through a single-degree-of-freedom (SDOF) oscillator which can be generically defined, assuming harmonic motion $q(t) = \hat{q}(\omega) e^{i\omega t}$, as:

$$\hat{m}\ddot{q} + \hat{k}q = \hat{F}_{mod}(\omega) e^{i\omega t} \quad (7)$$

with modal mass $\hat{m} = 1$ and modal stiffness $\hat{k} = \omega_n^2$. From eq. 7, the amplification factor, A_f , is defined as the ratio between the modal displacement amplitude, \hat{q} , and the modal

force amplitude, \hat{F}_{mod} , divided by the modal stiffness, \hat{k} , can be calculated as:

$$A_f = \frac{|\hat{q}|}{|\hat{F}_{mod}|/\hat{k}} = \frac{1}{1 - (\frac{\omega}{\omega_n})^2}. \quad (8)$$

Finally, the maximum displacement amplitude along the blade can be evaluated:

$$\Delta x_{max} = A_f \frac{|\hat{F}_{mod}|}{\hat{k}} \cdot \phi_{max} \quad (9)$$

with $\phi_{max} = \max|\phi(\mathbf{x})|$. This procedure allows for a direct evaluation of blade deflections induced by 1P loads, providing an estimate of the alternating stresses.

GLOBAL FORCES ON THE ROTOR

In this section, the global aerodynamic forces acting on the rotor blades are analyzed, their values are obtained by averaging the force terms over a revolution. The nacelle is excluded from the force balance since it corresponds to a simplified geometry, introduced solely for testing and validating aerodynamic methodologies, and does not reproduce the characteristics of a flight nacelle (i.e., it lacks both air intake and exhaust components).

The outlet guide vanes (OGVs) are not included in the force analysis. Being stationary components, the OGVs do not experience 1P excitations directly. However, when the inflow is inclined, they are subject to a non-uniform aerodynamic field that produces azimuthally varying loads. In the present work, their effect is considered only through the potential field they induce on the rotors. Due to the relatively large rotor–stator axial spacing and the low aerodynamic loads on the stators, this influence remains weak and is limited to low-order interactions.

The reference axes and azimuthal conventions adopted in this work are reported in Fig. 5. The azimuthal angle, θ , is measured positively in the direction of rotation. At the far-field boundary of the computational domain, a uniform flow is imposed with an inclination that generates the prescribed angle of attack, α , as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Figure 6 presents the variation of the thrust coefficient C_T (Fig. 6,a) and the in-plane force coefficient C_{1P} (Fig. 6,b) with the angle of attack α , for both take-off and cruise conditions. At take-off, C_T remains nearly constant over a wide range of angles of attack, with a slight increase at higher α due to the additional loading experienced by the advancing blades. In contrast, during cruise, a marked reduction of C_T is observed even for relatively small incidence angles. This behavior is consistent with the fact that, at $\alpha = 0$, the rotor operates close to its peak efficiency point [16]. Beyond this condition, the thin, low-cambered aerofoils of the open rotor exhibit limited incidence tolerance, leading to an early decrease in aerodynamic performance. Moreover, compressibility effects, associated with elevated relative Mach

FIGURE 6. ROTOR THRUST COEFFICIENT (A) AND IN-PLANE FORCE COEFFICIENT (B) AS A FUNCTION OF THE ANGLE OF ATTACK, α , FOR TAKE-OFF AND CRUISE.

numbers at cruise, further amplify profile losses and contribute to the reduction in thrust.

In Figure 6 b, a clear growth of C_{1P} with α is observed, due to the increasing asymmetry of the inflow field and the unbalanced loading between advancing and retreating blades. At cruise, C_{1P} increases sharply with α , reaching values as high as 70% of the thrust at $\alpha = 4^\circ$. At take-off, by contrast, the in-plane force coefficient remain comparatively smaller, with $C_{1P} \approx 0.48C_T$ at very high incidence angles ($\alpha = 30^\circ$). It is important to note that, in the nondimensional formulation, the factor $(\rho n^2 D^4)_{TO}/(\rho n^2 D^4)_{cr} = 4.76$ leads to substantially higher physical thrust at take-off relative to cruise, as expected. Nevertheless, the corresponding in-plane forces remain higher than in take-off underlining their relative

FIGURE 7. TAKE-OFF: ROTOR BLADE PRESSURE AT $\alpha = 10^\circ$. INSTANTANEOUS PRESSURE CONTOUR (A). NONDIMENSIONAL PRESSURE AT 50% SPAN FOR THREE REPRESENTATIVE AZIMUTHAL POSITIONS AND NONDIMENSIONAL PRESSURE OF THE STEADY SOLUTION AT $\alpha = 0^\circ$ (B).

FIGURE 8. CRUISE: ROTOR BLADE PRESSURE AT $\alpha = 4^\circ$. INSTANTANEOUS PRESSURE CONTOUR (A). NONDIMENSIONAL PRESSURE AT 50% SPAN FOR THREE REPRESENTATIVE AZIMUTHAL POSITIONS AND NONDIMENSIONAL PRESSURE OF THE STEADY SOLUTION AT $\alpha = 0^\circ$ (B).

importance for aeroelastic response.

Finally, the phase of the in-plane force remains essentially constant for each operating condition. At cruise, it stabilizes around $\Psi_{cr} = 18.0^\circ$, while at take-off it converges to $\Psi_{cr} = 25^\circ$. This stability of the phase indicates a well-defined directionality of the unsteady loading, which is relevant for the projection of the aerodynamic forces onto structural modes.

It should also be noted that a rotor operating under incidence generates aerodynamic moments about the three axes. The moment around the x-axis corresponds to the shaft torque, while the moments around the Y and Z axes originate from the force imbalance induced by the non-uniform inflow. Since the present

work is focused on the characterization of 1P loads, these additional moments fall outside its scope and will not be further discussed.

BLADE LOAD ANALYSIS

In this section, the unsteady aerodynamic loading on a single rotor blade is analyzed over a complete revolution, with the aim of identifying the influence of the angle of attack on the blade response. Unlike the previous discussion, where thrust and in-plane force coefficients were obtained by summing the contributions of all blades, here the coefficients are referred to

FIGURE 9. AZIMUTHAL BLADE THRUST AND IN-PLANE FORCE COEFFICIENT AT TAKE-OFF (A,B) AND CRUISE (C,D) AS A FUNCTION OF THE ANGLE OF ATTACK, α .

an individual blade to better capture the local variations, and therefore the time variations, induced by the asymmetric inflow.

Figure 7a presents the pressure distribution over the entire rotor at take-off conditions with $\alpha = 10^\circ$. The contour highlights the presence of a first engine-order pattern on the suction side of the blades, which is particularly evident at the mid-span sections. Figure 7b shows the pressure coefficient at 50% span for three different azimuthal positions, non-dimensionalized with the upstream dynamic pressure. For reference, the steady pressure distribution at zero angle of attack is also included, in order to magnify the relative changes introduced by the incidence. The results show that the suction side experiences the largest sensitivity to the azimuthal position, with a local unloading and reloading cycle following the advancing and retreating motion of the blade. On the pressure side, the variations are more moderate, with a load fluctuation of approximately 10% between the azimuthal positions $\theta = 90^\circ$ and $\theta = 270^\circ$, corresponding to the points of maximum and minimum loading, respectively. Analogously to the take-off condition, Figure 8 presents the pressure contour over the rotor blades and the instantaneous pressure distributions at three azimuthal positions for cruise at

FIGURE 10. SKETCH OF THE LOCAL REFERENCE SYSTEM WITH THE FORCE COMPONENTS.

$\alpha = 4$. The azimuthal variability of the pressure field becomes more pronounced due to the displacement of the shock front. The advancing blades experience a change in the axial position of the shock, whereas in the retreating side ($\theta = 270^\circ$) the shock vanishes completely.

To analyze the detailed 1P loads on the open rotor blade as a function of angle of attack (AoA), the blade thrust coefficient, C_T , and the in-plane force coefficient, C_{1P} , are plotted against the azimuthal position for several AoA at take-off (Fig. 9a–b) and cruise (Fig. 9c–d). At zero AoA, the simulations reveal small azimuthal fluctuations in C_T (Fig. 9a), which can be attributed to the potential aerodynamic influence of the downstream OGVs. As expected, this effect is minor and is only noticeable at takeoff, where the OGVs operate under higher loading. At cruise conditions, and for increasing AoA, these azimuthal fluctuations are practically negligible.

Two qualitative trends with the AoA can be observed. First, the radius of the polar curves increases with increasing AoA, particularly at takeoff, indicating that the magnitude of 1P oscillations grows with blade loading. Second, the center of the curves shifts when the AoA increases, reflecting a mean thrust imbalance compared with the the zero-AoA case.

Quantitatively, the maximum thrust occurs at the azimuthal position $\theta = 90^\circ$ where at take-off $C_T^{TO}(90^\circ)|_{\alpha=30} \approx 2.1 C_T^{TO}|_{\alpha=0}$ and at cruise $C_T^{cr}(90^\circ)|_{\alpha=6} \approx 1.9 C_T^{cr}|_{\alpha=0}$. On the other hand, the minimum thrust is observed at $\theta = 270^\circ$, with $C_T^{TO}(270^\circ)|_{\alpha=30} \approx 0.2 C_T^{TO}|_{\alpha=0}$ at take-off and $C_T^{cr}(270^\circ)|_{\alpha=6} \approx 0.1 C_T^{cr}|_{\alpha=0}$ at cruise. The magnitude of the in-plane force coefficient is notably higher at take-off, with $C_{1P}^{TO}(90^\circ)|_{\alpha=30} \approx 2 C_{1P}^{cr}|_{\alpha=6}$.

It is important to note that these simulations assume a rigid, non-rotating blade; thus, blade flexibility effects are not

FIGURE 11. TAKE-OFF: COMPARISON BETWEEN THE HARMONIC CONTENT OF THE BLADE FORCE COMPONENTS AT $\alpha = 0^\circ$ (BLUE LINES) AND $\alpha = 10^\circ$ (RED LINES).

accounted for in this analysis. Inclusion of structural dynamics in future work could reveal additional modulation of the 1P loads.

Harmonic content

To investigate the harmonic content of the blade loads, a frequency-domain analysis was performed by applying a Fourier Transform (FT) to the temporal force signals at takeoff and cruise conditions. The frequency spectrum was analyzed up to the 24th engine order, for which the temporal discretization provides sufficient resolution (30 samples per cycle).

Figure 11 presents the frequency spectra of the blade force components, expressed in the blade-relative coordinate system defined in Fig. 10, for the take-off condition at $\alpha = 0^\circ$ and $\alpha = 10^\circ$. The comparison shows that the AoA primarily amplifies the 1P component, while higher harmonics remain at much lower amplitudes. The analysis exhibits an amplitude of the first harmonic (1P component) is comparable to the mean (stationary) load, making it the dominant source of unsteady forcing on the blades.

FIGURE 12. CRUISE: COMPARISON BETWEEN THE HARMONIC CONTENT OF THE BLADE FORCE COMPONENTS AT $\alpha = 0^\circ$ (BLUE LINES) AND $\alpha = 2^\circ$ (RED LINES).

Similarly, Fig. 12 shows that the harmonic content at cruise is qualitatively similar to the takeoff case. The larger unsteady aerodynamic loading on the blade are directed to the axial and azimuthal directions in both operating conditions. Higher harmonics (2P, 3P, ...) are at least one order of magnitude smaller, confirming that the oscillatory blade dynamics are almost entirely governed by the 1P component.

ASSESSMENT OF THE 1P LOADS

The thrust and in-plane load coefficients reported in Fig. 9, together with the harmonic decomposition of Fig. 11 and 12, indicate that variations in blade angle of attack generate a periodic modulation of the aerodynamic loads along the azimuth. The harmonic analysis confirms that the 1P component is the dominant source of unsteady excitation of the rotor under incidence. To first approximation, this modulation can be represented by a simple harmonic function. For each operating point, the normalized thrust coefficient may thus be expressed as:

FIGURE 13. NORMALIZED OSCILLATION AMPLITUDE, k , AS A FUNCTION OF THE ANGLE OF ATTACK FOR TAKE-OFF AND CRUISE.

$$\tilde{C}_t(\theta) = \frac{C_t(\theta)}{\bar{C}_t} = 1 + k \sin(\theta + \chi). \quad (10)$$

The thrust coefficient has been normalized with its average value, calculated as:

$$\bar{C}_t = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} C_t(\theta) d\theta \quad (11)$$

The parameter $k = C'_t / \bar{C}_t$ represents the ratio between the amplitude of the oscillation, which is approximated by the difference between the maximum and minimum of the C_t :

$$C'_t = (C_t^{Max} - C_t^{Min}) / 2 \quad (12)$$

and the mean thrust coefficient. Figure 9 highlights that $C_t^{Max} \approx C_t(90^\circ)$ and $C_t^{Min} \approx C_t(270^\circ)$. The phase shift χ is referenced to the azimuthal position $\theta = 0^\circ$:

$$\chi = \arcsin\left(\frac{C_t(0^\circ) - \bar{C}_t}{C'_t}\right). \quad (13)$$

For take-off and cruise the phase angle $\chi \simeq 0^\circ$. A similar normalized expression can be also formulated for the off-axis 1P components, C_{1P} .

When plotting C'_t as a function of angle of attack (Fig. 13), the trend exhibits an almost linear relationship within each operating condition. As a result, the first-harmonic content of the unsteady load grows approximately linearly with the AoA, $k = \lambda \alpha$, where $\lambda = \tan \epsilon$. Equation 10 is then expressed as:

$$\tilde{C}_t(\theta) = 1 + \lambda \alpha \sin(\theta + \chi). \quad (14)$$

This approximation is a reasonable description of thrust variation, as seen in Fig. 14. The angle ϵ^{TO} encapsulates the sensitivity of the first-harmonic on multiple flow and blade parameters, including blade pitch settings, dynamic pressure, rotational speed, and Mach number. Its determination is therefore complex and deferred to future work.

FIGURE 14. NORMALIZED THRUST COEFFICIENT, \tilde{C}_t , AS A FUNCTION OF THE AZIMUTHAL ANGLE FOR TAKE-OFF AND CRUISE. COMPARISON BETWEEN THE CFD DATA AND THE SINGLE HARMONIC APPROXIMATION.

FIGURE 15. MODULE OF THE 1P UNSTEADY FORCE, F'_{Tot} , NONDIMENSIONALIZED WITH THE MODULE OF BLADE FORCE RESULTANT, AT TAKE-OFF WITH $\alpha = 0^\circ$, $F_{Tot}^{TO} |_{\alpha=0}$, AS A FUNCTION OF THE AoA.

Figure 15 quantifies the amplitude of this harmonic as a function of AoA for both take-off and cruise, normalized with respect to the steady resultant force at $\alpha = 0^\circ$. A given increment in angle of attack generates a proportionally larger oscillatory load at cruise compared to take-off (i.e. $F_{Tot}^{l,cr}(6^\circ) = F_{Tot}^{l,TO}(10^\circ)$).

Figures 16 and 17 present the distribution of the unsteady pressure on the blade surface, expressed in terms of the modulus of the first harmonic of pressure at two representative sections, located at 50% and 80% span, for different angles of attack at take-off and cruise conditions. The unsteady pressure amplitude is normalized with the local dynamic pressure to allow a direct comparison between operating points. At take-off (Fig. 16a), the

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 16. TAKE-OFF: 1P UNSTEADY PRESSURE CONTOUR AT $\alpha = 10^\circ$ AND $\alpha = 30^\circ$ (A). NONDIMENSIONAL UNSTEADY PRESSURE (FIRST HARMONIC) AT 50% SPAN AND 80% SPAN (B).

unsteady load is mainly concentrated close to the leading edge, where the amplitude reaches up to 6% of the dynamic pressure, reflecting the strong incidence sensitivity of the leading-edge suction peak. In cruise (Fig. 17), the distribution is markedly different: the contours reveal the presence of a shock wave, whose position is clearly traced by the maximum unsteady pressure. The interaction between the shock displacement and the incoming disturbances produces a localized amplification of the oscillatory pressure which is clear at mid-span (50% span section).

MODAL FORCES

The unsteady aerodynamic forcing associated with the 1P frequency component was projected onto the first bending mode of the blade to obtain the modal force as described in Eq. 4.

(a)

(b)

FIGURE 17. CRUISE: 1P UNSTEADY PRESSURE CONTOUR AT $\alpha = 2^\circ$ AND $\alpha = 4^\circ$ (A). NONDIMENSIONAL UNSTEADY PRESSURE (FIRST HARMONIC) AT 50% SPAN AND 80% SPAN (B).

A comparison between the modal forces and the first harmonic of the unsteady blade loads shows that the overall trend of the curves remains similar at both operating points, on the contrary the magnitudes differ. This similarity indicates that increasing the angle of attack the blade load distribution of 1P harmonic does not alter the projection onto the structural mode.

At take-off, the modal forces increase approximately linearly with angle of attack. From Eq. 6, the sensitivity of the modal force can be expressed as:

$$\frac{\partial \hat{F}_{mod}(\omega)}{\partial \alpha} = \int_{\Sigma} \frac{\partial \hat{p}(\mathbf{x}, \omega)}{\partial \alpha} (\phi(\mathbf{x}) \cdot \mathbf{n}(\mathbf{x})) dS \approx const. \quad (15)$$

This indicates that the incremental unsteady loads are smoothly redistributed across the blade without major nonlinear flow features.

In contrast, the behavior at cruise is more complex and the correlation between the unsteady pressure field, $\hat{p}(\mathbf{x}, \omega)$, and the

FIGURE 18. MODAL FORCE, F_{mod} , NONDIMENSIONALIZED WITH NONDIMENSIONALIZED WITH THE MODULE OF THE FORCE RESULTANT, AT TAKE-OFF WITH $\alpha = 0^\circ$, $F_{Tot}^{TO}|_{\alpha=0}$, AS A FUNCTION OF THE AoA.

structural mode shape, $\phi(\mathbf{x})$, evolves progressively reducing the growth rate of the modal force. It is also worth noting that at cruise, inflow angles of 4–6° represent extreme conditions that are unlikely to be encountered during standard flight operations, reinforcing the practical relevance of the small-angle regime. For small angles of attack, the sensitivity of the modal force is nearly constant across operating points.

The aerodynamic excitation contains contributions from multiple harmonics of the rotor frequency. The structural response is modeled as a single-degree-of-freedom system (see Eq. 7). As shown in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, the dominant component is the first per-rev frequency, $\omega = 1\Omega$, which is considered in the present analysis. Higher harmonics (2P, 3P, ...) are neglected. From the Campbell diagram shown in Fig. 3, the first flexural frequency margin with respect to the 1st engine order (EO1) can be derived, yielding a value of 56% at takeoff and 74% at cruise.

At cruise, the 2nd engine order (EO2) lies closer to the first flexural natural frequency, with a reduced margin of approximately 25%. However, because the harmonic amplitude associated with EO2 is comparatively weak, its contribution to the dynamic response is not considered critical and has therefore been neglected in the oscillation analysis.

The structural response can be seen as the sum of deformations due to steady loads plus the dynamic contribution from the 1P component. Since CFD simulations were performed with rigid blades, static deformations are not included here, and only the dynamic oscillatory part is evaluated.

The resulting physical oscillations can differ substantially

FIGURE 19. DYNAMIC AMPLIFICATION FACTOR, A_f .

AoA [deg]	$\Delta x_{max}/H$ [%]
Take-off	
10	0.39
20	0.72
30	1
Cruise	
2	0.15
4	0.28
6	0.38

TABLE 3. BLADE MAXIMUM DISPLACEMENTS AS A FUNCTION OF THE AoA FOR TAKE-OFF AND CRUISE. THE VALUES ARE NONDIMENSIONALIZED WITH THE BLADE SPAN, H .

because the structural response is governed not only by the magnitude of the modal force but also by the amplification factor associated with each mode. This factor depends on the excitation frequency as expressed in Eq. 8, which varies with rotor speed. In the present analysis, the amplification factors are sketched in Fig. 19 and are $A_f|_{cr} = 1.49$ for cruise and $A_f|_{TO} = 1.69$ for the take-off. Although the amplification at cruise is slightly lower than at takeoff, the dynamic response is more severe at cruise due to stronger modal forcing. Finally, the oscillation amplitudes were computed using Eq. 9 and non-dimensionalized with respect to the blade span, $H = 1.32$ m. Table 3 is summarizing the maximum blade oscillations for both operating

conditions. The results show that, for both operating conditions, the maximum normalized tip oscillations ($\Delta x_{max}/H$) remain below 1%. This indicates that the structural vibrations induced by the aerodynamic excitation are relatively small compared to the blade span, and therefore unlikely to compromise structural integrity or significantly affect aerodynamic performance within the analyzed conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a CFD-based methodology for assessing the dynamic response of an Open Rotor subjected to inflow angles representative of takeoff and cruise conditions. The approach combines full-annulus unsteady simulations with modal force projection and a simplified structural response model. The results confirm that the 1P harmonic dominates the unsteady aerodynamic loads. The global forces were decomposed into thrust and in-plane components, expressed in nondimensional form to facilitate performance-oriented comparison across operating conditions. Subsequently, the unsteady pressure field was projected onto the first bending mode of the blade, yielding the modal force.

The structural response is amplified by the dynamic response of the blade but nonetheless remains modest, with normalized tip oscillations below 1% of the span in all cases. The results show that the blade dynamic response is governed not only by the magnitude of the unsteady aerodynamic loads, but also by their modal alignment with the structural mode. This highlights the necessity of employing modal forces, rather than raw harmonic loads, when estimating physical oscillations and fatigue-critical stresses.

The methodology relies on a number of simplifications, as it considers only the first bending mode, retains solely the 1P harmonic, and assumes rigid-blade aerodynamics without fluid–structure interaction. Despite these assumptions, the approach captures the essential physics of the aerodynamic excitation and its structural response making the method reliable for preliminary design and fatigue assessment of open-fan blades.

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